

TEACHING GRAMMAR: APPROACHES AND ACTIVITIES FOR ESL/EFL CLASSROOMS

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Abstract

Grammar is a dynamic and evolving process, shaping language and improving its harmony and clarity (Thornbury, 2001). For teachers, understanding the core importance of grammar and creating optimal teaching conditions is essential. Teaching English grammar in non-native environments can be particularly challenging, with teachers and students encountering numerous obstacles in ESL/EFL classrooms (Al-Mekhlafi, 2011). To enhance learning outcomes, educators must clearly consider key points in grammar instruction and employ techniques suitable for productive assessment. This article discusses three principal approaches to grammar instruction—teaching grammar as a product, as a process, and as a skill—exploring each approach's methods, benefits, and limitations.

Grammar as a Product

The product approach to grammar instruction emphasizes accuracy and the mastery of grammatical forms through structured, form-focused activities. This method centers on the completion of activities with the correct use of grammatical structures, often in a graded or assessed format. Activities in this approach can be teacher-created or pre-made, typically designed to prompt students to identify and manipulate grammatical forms through guided practice. Students may be asked to complete worksheets or exercises before formal instruction, allowing them to distinguish grammatical forms before learning their functions in depth. This approach, as La Rocque (1971) argues, prioritizes knowledge acquisition, making the understanding of grammar a primary goal. Ellis expands on the product approach by suggesting that this form-centered system provides "intake facilitation," meaning that as students notice and practice forms, these grammatical features become reinforced in their memory. An example of this can be seen in activities where students are required to complete sentences using the Present Perfect tense. In a textbook-based activity, students may rewrite sentences by filling in blanks or by arranging words in the correct sequence. In an online setting, they might complete similar exercises,

with the advantage of instant feedback that allows for repeated attempts until the correct answer is achieved.

The product approach has several benefits, particularly in fostering accuracy and retention. However, it has limitations as well. A lack of self-discovery in structured activities may stifle student creativity, as learners are often bound to follow specific forms and sequences without engaging their own ideas. Additionally, most product-based activities offer only evaluative marks without providing insight into students' errors, which might prevent deeper learning. To address this, teachers could use error analysis, discussing common mistakes and exploring the reasons behind them with students. Adding interactive elements, such as role-play, can also enhance engagement by allowing students to practice grammar forms more dynamically.

Grammar as a Process

The process approach to teaching grammar focuses on meaning and self-expression rather than rigid accuracy. Unlike the product approach, it encourages students to explore grammar in a more flexible, discovery-based format. Process-oriented activities often adopt a "task-based" format, in which students use grammar within broader, meaningful language tasks that require self-expression and problem-solving. Candlin (1987) describes process-based tasks as adaptable, allowing learners to experiment with language use while reflecting their personal attitudes and perspectives.

In this approach, grammatical rules are not provided in advance; instead, students are encouraged to discover grammar patterns independently. For example, a task might involve describing pictures using passive forms without explicit guidance, prompting students to rely on their knowledge and creativity. The absence of strict regulation within process teaching shifts the focus away from precise accuracy, aiming instead for fluency and the clear communication of ideas. This allows students to express themselves more freely, building their confidence in using language creatively.

While this approach fosters fluency and builds a supportive learning environment, it can be time-intensive and may lead to misunderstandings if grammar rules are not sufficiently clarified. Some students might prioritize fluency over accuracy, resulting in grammatical errors. To address these potential challenges, teachers can combine the process approach with the product approach, briefly reviewing key grammar structures before allowing students to explore language use freely. This method provides a framework that supports self-expression while promoting a basic understanding of grammar.

Grammar as a Skill

Teaching grammar as a skill emphasizes integrating grammar learning into practical language skills, such as reading and listening, within authentic contexts. This approach involves using grammatical forms within real-life scenarios, helping students understand their relevance in everyday situations. Rob Batstone (1994) argues that attention to grammar within contextual language learning can enhance both comprehension and retention of grammatical structures.

For example, in a listening-based activity, students may listen to a track describing daily routines and arrange a series of pictures in the correct order, followed by filling in blanks with the appropriate Present Simple forms. This activity not only reinforces Present Simple usage but also improves listening skills, as students must pay close attention to identify the sequence of events described. In another task, students might complete sentences about daily routines, realizing through practice that the Present Simple is typically used for habitual actions.

The skill approach offers the advantage of context-based learning, helping students see the practical applications of grammar in real-life situations. It can be particularly engaging as students relate these activities to familiar scenarios, making grammar instruction feel more relevant and approachable. However, these tasks require careful planning to ensure a balance between grammatical focus and authentic language use. Personalizing these activities—such as having students describe their own routines using the same grammar—can further enhance engagement by making learning more meaningful and memorable.

Conclusion

Each approach to teaching grammar—whether viewed as product, process, or skill—brings unique strengths and challenges to the classroom. While the product approach fosters accuracy and reinforces the structure, the process approach emphasizes creativity and expression, promoting a supportive environment for self-discovery. Meanwhile, the skill approach encourages the application of grammar in real-world contexts, making it more practical and relatable for students.

Combining these methods can create a more holistic grammar curriculum that supports both accuracy and fluency. By tailoring activities to individual student needs and providing meaningful feedback, educators can make grammar

instruction engaging and effective, supporting students on their journey toward language proficiency.

References:

1. Al-Mekhlafi, A. (2011). Difficulties in Teaching and Learning Grammar in an EFL Context. *International Journal of Instruction*.
2. Atalya, A. (2017). The Analysis of English Language Education Students' Teaching Skills During Microteaching: Product-Processed Approach to Teaching Grammar. *English Language Education*.
3. Bassey, M. (1999). *Case Study Research in Educational Settings*. Buckingham: Open University Press.
4. Batstone, R. (1994). *Grammar*. Oxford University Press.
5. La Rocque, G. E. (1971). English Curriculum: Process or Product? *The English Journal*.
6. Thornbury, S. (1999). *How to Teach Grammar*. Pearson Education Limited.